

BADI WOMEN AND PROSTITUTION IN NEPAL: A COMPREHENSIVE PERSPECTIVE ON RIGHTS AND SOCIAL JUSTICE

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Abstract

Every human being is inherently free and equal in rights and dignity. All members of society possess the same intrinsic worth, regardless of their social standing, heritage, traditions, cultural background, or community practices. Denying any individual or community to the exercise of fundamental human rights is an injustice that undermines the principles of fairness and poses a threat to the broader human community and the essence of humanity. The Badi community of Nepal has long been associated with prostitution as a customary tradition (Pratha), a practice deeply intertwined with historical, cultural, and socio-economic paradigms. This paper explores the origins, evolution, and implications of this practice, examining its impact on human rights, gender equality, and societal perceptions. This study examines the cultural framework of prostitution and its impact on the status of women within the Badi community through an analytical lens. The research seeks to explore and critically address the cultural norms and traditional attitudes toward women and their bodies, emphasizing the issue of sexual exploitation faced by women in the Badi community. The study employs a multidisciplinary approach, analyzing historical accounts, legal frameworks, and identifies pathways for reform necessitating for human dignity, women rights and social justice.

Keywords: Badi Community, Badi women, Customary Practices, Prostitution, Gender Inequality, Sexual exploitation, Human Rights, Women Rights, Social Justice.

METHODS

This study adopts a comprehensive qualitative methodology, encompassing doctrinal legal analysis, secondary data, and institutional frameworks. These methods are utilized to systematically explore and define the conceptualization of 'Badi Pratha' as a manifestation of sexual exploitation while examining the customary systems and societal positioning of women in the Badi community. Additionally, it includes critical discourse analysis of theoretical literature and an objective appraisal of factual studies focused on the rights of Badi women. The study endeavors to deliver a comprehensive assessment of prostitution as a customary practice within the Badi community and evaluates the legal structures governing women's rights of Badi women in Nepal.

1. GENERAL CONTEXT AND SOCIAL STATUS OF WOMEN: AN OVERVIEW

Across diverse societies, it is customary to classify the human population primarily into categories of 'men' and 'women' (not excluding other genders), with distinctions often

rooted in biological sex differences. These differences have been further entrenched by societal norms, practices, and cultural expectations that define the roles and statuses of men, women and Gender-Diverse Populations (LGBTIQA+ Communities, Gender Expansive Groups). A historical analysis of human society reveals that women, in no society, have attained complete equality with men. Inequality, discrimination, and exploitation have been pervasive. Globally, women face marginalization, violations of their freedoms, and exploitation of their sexuality- prostitution being a prominent fact. This persists despite the recognition of women's human rights, international human rights standards, and the outcome of prolonged struggles and movements for gender equality. Gender discrimination predominantly manifests as discrimination against women (including gender minorities) and remains a pervasive issue throughout human civilizations. This form of inequality, rooted in sex-based distinctions, is not merely a legal concept but a complex social phenomenon arising from a confluence of cultural, social, and institutional factors. Regrettably, legal systems have historically legitimized discriminatory practices, reflecting and reinforcing societal and cultural traditions. These practices perpetuate gender stereotypes, contributing to the suppression and marginalization of women, leading to widespread violence and a deterioration of their societal status. These practices absolutely reflect and perpetuate societal norms and stereotypes about masculinity and femininity, contributing to the reinforcement of gender inequality, gender differentiation and gender system (Roka, 2024). 'Violence against women' means any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion, or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life (Article1, DEVAW).

"Violence against women shall be understood to encompass, but not be limited to: a) Physical, sexual and psychological violence occurring in the family, including battering, sexual abuse of female children in the household, dowry-related violence, marital rape, female genital mutilation and other traditional practices harmful to women, non-spousal violence and violence related to exploitation; b) Physical, sexual and psychological violence occurring within the general community, including rape, sexual abuse, sexual harassment and intimidation at work, in educational institutions and elsewhere, trafficking in women and forced prostitution; c) Physical, sexual and psychological violence perpetrated or condoned by the State, wherever it occurs" (Article 2, DEVAW). Such violence is intrinsically tied to women's subordinate position in patriarchal societies, where systemic inequalities are entrenched in social, cultural, political, and economic structures. Patriarchy as a system that allocates societal rights, privileges, and power based on gender, subordinating women while privileging men (Lewis, 2022). Patriarchy and gendered system not only render women vulnerable to violence but also obstructs their access to justice by silencing their voices, denying the existence of abuse, and limiting remedies. A significant area of women's subjugation lies in their sexuality, which patriarchal norms exploit as a means of control and oppression. Women's oppression is the most fundamental form of oppression (Feminist thought, 2022). In male-dominated societies, women are often denied autonomy over their bodies and sexuality, perpetuating

their inferior status. 'Women are alienated as a consequence of the construction of their sexuality in male terms (Mackinnon, 2012). This systemic inequality has created a cultural environment prone to sexual offenses, where such acts are used to exert control through force, violence, or coercion, that reinforces and perpetuates the objectification, subordination, and exploitation of women (Feminist thought, 2022). Sexual violence encompasses any acts or conducts that violate an individual's sex and sexuality, instances include of rape, sexual harassment, stalking, molestation, eve teasing, bigamy, fraudulent marriages, adultery, enticement of married women, abduction, kidnapping, human trafficking, coerced prostitution, sexual slavery, verbal abuse, humiliation, threats, cyber harassment, revenge porn, catfishing for exploitation, online grooming, deep fake pornography, sextortion, digital stalking, non-consensual live streaming, unsolicited explicit content, and other related offenses. Sexual offence is a 'direct expression of sexual politics, a ritual enactment of male domination, and a form of terror that functions to maintain the status quo' (Caputi, 2022).

The subordinate position of women became an accepted cultural norm for the majority section of the population until the beginning of the nineteenth century (Kant, 1997). The situation is no different for today as well. Females are taken as sexual commodity, private jurisdiction of male. Subordination of women exists because there is social exclusion and social stigma. Even today many decades after independence, women are suffering from such abuse in society (Ashraf, 1997). Forced prostitution or other kinds of commercial exploitation by male partners or parents in another form of violence against women and children reported worldwide. In certain hill districts of Nepal, prostitution has become an almost traditional source of income. In southern India where young women and girls (Devadasis) are donated, to serve a temple and very often end up being prostituted (Padma & Rao, 2011). There is a dearth of official data on the prevalence of violence against women in Nepal, but non-governmental sources have reported a high prevalence of various forms of violence, including rape, sexual abuse, domestic violence, dowry related violence, sexual harassment in the workplace, trafficking of women and children, and traditional cultural forms of violence (the center for Reproductive Rights, 2004). Contextualizing Nepalese girls into the commercial sexual exploitation, within and outside the country, has been a reality for long time, and is considered a major human rights issue. Mostly invisible to the mainstream society (mainly because of the social taboo attached with issues of prostitution and sex outside marriage), the horrifying nature of this exploitation has emerged from the visible socio-legal and cultural discrimination, and economic deprivation suffered by the female population in Nepal (Regmi, 2003). A study on women's status in Nepal reveals their secondary status and resulting oppression because of the dominant Hindu religion and prevailing social and cultural norms in the country (FWLD, 2006).

The Badi system is a deeply ingrained and flawed customary practice in Nepal, where prostitution is entrenched as a socio-cultural norm, leading to the exploitation of Badi women. The Badi system is a traditional form of sexual violence, rooted in the commodification and objectification of women's bodies, reinforcing their subjugation and marginalization. This practice dehumanizes women, stripping them of dignity and self-

worth, and entraps them in a cycle of self-sacrifice dictated by customary beliefs, which often leads to their forced involvement in prostitution. These practices constitute crimes against women's integrity, violations of women's rights, breaches of human dignity, and contradictions to both constitutional and legal principles. Badi women are ensnared as victims of systemic oppression, societal stigma, and coercive circumstances, stigmatized as 'fallen women' or Badini, and unfairly labeled as prostitutes.

2. COMPREHENDING AND CHARACTERIZING THE BADI SYSTEM

The Badi community represents one of the most strikingly affected groups within Nepal's rigid caste hierarchy. For generations, this sub-caste has been confined to prostitution, perpetuated by deeply entrenched traditions. As a unique segment of Nepal's Dalit or 'marginalized' caste, the Badi possess their own cultural practices, linguistic characteristic of Nepali, and distinctive social structures. The Badi people moved to western Nepal from North India in the 1700s, travelling in groups of three families and working as entertainers, staging dance and musical performances and telling stories from Hindu epics (such as epics of Mahabharat and Ramayana) at festivals, weddings or private parties (Badi Prostitution, Slavery in Nepal, 2022).

Ancient legends suggest that the Badi people are descendants of the celestial Gandharva Apsaras, and their lifestyle, which combined dance, art, and prostitution, is said to reflect that of the Gandharva fairies. The term Badi is derived from the Sanskrit word Vadyabadak and means 'one who plays musical instruments', referring to the period when they were a caste of nomadic entertainers in neighboring Indian states as Bihar and Uttar Pradesh (UNRC/HC Nepal, 2022). Badi are an untouchable Hindu caste, with a total population of approximately 7,000, who inhabit scattered settlements in the Salyan, Rolpa, Rukum, Dailekh, Seti, Jajarkot, Dang-Dekhuri, Banke and Bardiya Districts of west Nepal. Badi men fish (keeping most of the catch for their own family's consumption) and make drums and pipes, which they sell to Nepalese in neighboring communities.

Badi women prostitute themselves, beginning at puberty and continuing until they become too old to attract any more customers, or get married (Cox, 2022). Badi community made up of 0.1% of Nepal's population (CBS Nepal, 2021). Nepal's 1854 Civil Code categorized the Badi community as the lowest among the socially and economically disadvantaged Dalit caste (Gurung, 2005).

The Badi people were historically recognized as artists, possessing innate talents in dance, music, and entertainment, which served as their primary means of livelihood. During earlier times, their professional obligations centered around providing entertainment, and Badi women restricted their involvement in prostitution to serving royal patrons, relatives, and a limited number of clients.

However, significant social and political changes occurred following the overthrow of the autocratic Rana regime in 1950 and the subsequent establishment of the Panchayat system. These changes stripped ousted rulers and landlords in western Nepal of their authority, including their rights to levy taxes and retain unpaid laborers. Under the

patronage of the kings of Salyan, Jajarkot, and Musikot, Badi women once held the status of high-class courtesans. By the 1950s, however, the community lost its royal benefactors, and the advent of mass entertainment diminished the value of their artistic skills, such as singing, dancing, and crafting madals or musical instruments. As a result, sex work became a primary source of income for Badi women, and they grew less selective about their clientele. This dependency increased after the 1960 plague in the hill regions, which prompted migration and brought an influx of clients to the areas where the Badi community resided.

Over time, prostitution became the dominant source of livelihood for the Badi community, Badi women turned to prostitution as they found it unsustainable to rely solely on dancing and singing for their livelihood. Consequently, the commodification of their bodies became an entrenched practice evolving into a professional identity, cultural norm, and customary value within the Badi community. Badi community has been suffering from the vicious circle of caste-based discrimination and untouchability for ages. The impacts of ill-treatment and sexual violence faced by the Badi women has resulted in difficult livelihoods for the children of this community (Nepal Human Rights Year Book, 2022).

The Badi community has experienced persistent economic, social, cultural, and political marginalization. Over the years, they have been neglected by the State, disregarded, exploited, and socially excluded. The children of this community have endured discrimination due to factors such as poverty, lack of education, unemployment, superstitions, traditional customs, and the inadequate enforcement of laws (Nepal Human Rights Year Book, 2022). The prominent areas associated with the Badi community include Ghorahi and Tulsipur (Dang), Nepalgunj (Banke), Rajapur (Bardiya), and Satti (Kailali).

Throughout history, societies have witnessed recurring patterns in their social structures, albeit in varied forms and expressions. Practices once recognized as *Nagarvadhu* or *Nagarshovini* in ancient times have evolved into the *Badini* tradition within the Badi community. For generations, Badi women and girls have been professional sex workers, with the *Badi Pratha* emerging as a harmful and degrading cultural practice in Nepal. This system carries profound repercussions for the dignity, rights, and well-being of the women coerced into this customary role.

Institutionalized sexual violence and exploitation characterize the *Badi Pratha*, which starkly illustrates how customs and traditions can perpetuate and legitimize extreme cruelty against women within families and communities. This cultural practice imposes stringent sexual codes, leading to stigmatization and severe harm to women's dignity, sanctity, liberty, integrity and freedom. Sexual objectification of women, sexual dominance, sexual submissiveness, indignity and oppression, exploitation, systematically extended reactionary traditions against women are elements of Phallocentric culture and customary practice in Badi community. *Badi Pratha* is thus a deeply defective tradition that threatens the fundamental rights and dignity of Badi women and their community, exemplifying the enduring power of oppressive customs and their far-reaching consequences.

2.1 Badi Movement: An Overview

The Badi community has been constantly waging legal battles and protesting on the streets for their rights, justice and development:¹

Key Events	Year
Migration of Badi communities from the hill regions of Mid-Western and Far-Western Nepal to the plains, including Dang, Banke, Bardiya, Kailali, and Kanchanpur districts.	1960 onwards
Formation of various non-governmental organizations advocating for the rights of the Badi community, such as Samaj Sudhar Sewa Sangh (1991), SAFE Nepal (1992), and Dalit Ekata Mahila Kendra (2000).	1991-2000
Launch of the first organized nonviolent movement by the Badi community, known as the Gaganjung Movement.	2001
Convening of the First National Assembly of Badi Women in Nepal.	31 January 2002
Advocacy campaigns and protests in the Mid-Western and Far-Western regions, demanding either licensing for sex work to support livelihoods or alternative means of livelihood for sex workers.	2003-2007
Formation of a government-led committee under the Ministry of Women, Children, and Social Welfare, involving representatives from the Dalit Commission, Badi community, and other stakeholders to address the community's challenges.	20 May 2004
Supreme Court directive to the Nepalese government to ensure the rights of Badi women.	15 September 2005
Establishment of the Badi Struggle Committee under Uma Devi Badi's leadership, organizing a 48-day nonviolent protest in Kathmandu.	17 August 2007-15 October 2007
Creation of the Badi Development Board to tackle the socio-economic issues faced by the Badi community.	2012

Fig: Timeline of Badi Movements in Nepal

Despite the commitments made in the *2006 Interim Constitution* and the *Comprehensive Peace Agreement* to eliminate discrimination and safeguard the rights of women and marginalized groups, the Badi community continues to endure severe socio-economic exclusion. Restricted access to essential services, limited employment opportunities, and the absence of land ownership have perpetuated widespread poverty within the community. Badi women, in particular, suffer from discriminatory practices and social stigmatization stemming from their perceived association with prostitution. The struggles of the Badi community gained national recognition following the *Badi Andolan* (Badi Movement) of August 2007, during which a group of Badi women, dressed only in petticoats, staged a semi-nude protest at the main entrance of Singha Durbar to demand their rights and alternative livelihoods. This demonstration captured significant media attention and was widely reported in major newspapers. The pressing concern now revolves around the present circumstances of the Badi community in Nepal. The factors such as discrimination, social stigma and exclusion being the community's main challenges have contributed to their socioeconomic marginalization in Nepali society (UNRC/ HC Nepal, 2012). The Supreme Court of Nepal granted formal citizenship to members of the Badi community and directed the government to implement retraining and alternative employment programs while providing financial assistance to

impoverished families. The government committed to examining the challenges faced by the Badi community and pledged support through land grants, employment training, free education for Badi children, access to healthcare, citizenship under their chosen caste, and a formal declaration to end prostitution within the community. On December 28, 2008, the Council of Ministers declared Badi women free from sexual exploitation. Subsequently, on January 7, 2009, the government announced plans to rehabilitate the Badi community by allocating land and equipping them with income-generating skills. Even years after the announcement, the decision remains unimplemented, leaving the Badi community still grappling with sexual abuse and stigma as sex workers. Their challenges intensify during the rainy season, with rental houses deteriorating. “We have to seek refuge at relatives' homes for safety,” shared Gita Badi. Initially, the Badi community held hope that local government intervention would bring positive change, but Sangita Badi expresses that their optimism is now fading into despair (Bista, 2022). Today, the Badi community faces limited access to education, healthcare, land ownership, and citizenship. The majority of Badi individuals are illiterate, with teachers and children from higher castes often excluding them and other low-caste Dalits from classrooms. About one-third of the Badi population is homeless, while two-thirds reside on public or government land. Nearly 75% of Badi men migrate in search of work, leaving women and children to manage on their own. These complex factors have created the devastating reality that Prostitution and selling girls to traffickers have become sources of income for many Badi families (Tracey, 2022). Since the government’s declaration has turned into a fragile hope and unfulfilled promises, the Badi community remains marginalized, living in poverty and neglected by the state. Badi women persist in facing lives marked by degradation, subjugation, exploitation, oppression, persecution, marginalization, repression and numerous hardships.

3. PROSTITUTION AND PROSTITUTIONAL OPPRESSION

Prostitution, the act of engaging in sexual activity, typically with individuals who are not spouses or friends, in exchange for immediate compensation in money or other valuables. Sex workers may be female, male, or transgender, and the work can involve either heterosexual or homosexual interactions. Historically, however, most sex workers have been women, and the majority of clients have been men. Perceptions of prostitution are based on culturally determined values that differ between societies (Jenkins, 2022). Prostitution refers to the exchange of sexual services for money, often seen as the commercial or mercenary practice of engaging in promiscuous sexual activity. The term “prostitute” comes from the Latin word *prostituta*, where “pro” means “in front” or “forward” and “siture” refers to “to offer for sale”. A literal translation would be “to put up for sale” or “to present for trade”. Prostitution is the most effective instrument of sexual objectification of women in the society and thereby placing them in a subordinated and marginalized condition (Lerner, 1986). As pointed out by Rubin (1994), in the very creation of society, women were allegedly subordinated through ritual exchange in order to create bonds of kinship among men as the foundation of the social order. This practice eventually led to the establishment of a structured system for the commercial exchange of women,

formalizing prostitution. The exploitative nature of prostitution is deliberately designed to subjugate and degrade women. Historically, therefore, both the practice and institution of prostitution lack any aspects that could be celebrated or regarded as a positive contribution to human culture and civilization. In Asia, however, states did not adopt overt regulatory approaches but instead tacitly acknowledged prostitution as a prevalent social phenomenon. Historically, many rulers in Asian nations operated brothels within their palaces. The present presidents and prime ministers turn a blind eye to the exploitation of hundreds of girls and women in the so-called red-light areas of their countries (Friedman, 2017). Prostitution is a severe form of exploitation. The sexual services provided by sex workers undermine the dignity of all women and humanity as a whole. Prostitution as a menace is essentially an outcome of sex delinquency; Donald Taft observed that “our attitude towards prostitution varies from approval through acceptance and tolerance to violent opposition as ‘Prostitutes life’ (Francis, 1960). Prostitution is fundamentally a system of exploitation and devaluation of women. Millions of women and girls, both historically and in the present day, are trapped in sexual slavery within brothels and other venues, deceived and trafficked specifically for this purpose. Even in such cases, the women are ‘prostitutes’ with all the contempt the word connotes, and the male users of these sexual slaves are merely ‘men’ with all their social standing intact”. It is the prototype, the model from which all other sexual exploitation can be understood (Hofmann, 1995).

Prostitution is a deceptive alternative to rape (Cunha, 2022). Prostitution is considered society’s safety valve against the rape of innocent women and the disintegration of the institution of family (Cunha, 1992). Prostitution operates as a market system comprising five key elements: a) the state and society, which indirectly endorse this system of human exploitation; b) pimps and traffickers, who profit from the commodification of women’s and girls’ bodies; c) male clients, who purchase access to various parts of the body- vagina, anus, breasts, mouth, and hands, treating them as objects for their gratification; d) the women involved, who are victims of this system, forced to endure repeated violations of their dignity and physical well-being to survive, suffering immense harm to their bodies and spirits from men for whom they feel no desire; and e) money, which plays a central role in perpetuating the global sex trade, enabling regulatory measures that sanitize billions of illicit dollars and lend legitimacy to organized crime by normalizing the trade in women’s bodies as a form of work (Butler, 2022). This very elaborate system, like other systems of domination, is mainly based on the silence of victims, the women in prostitution, and denial of the fact that this system is violence against women (Marcovish, 2010). “Prostitution inherently inflicts harm upon women”. Regardless of its form, prostitution victimizes women, often at the expense of their well-being and lives. The violation of their right to a dignified existence is among its gravest consequences. It dehumanizes women, causing severe physical and psychological harm, posing a significant threat to their overall existence. The damage caused by prostitution remains largely invisible-socially, legally, within public health systems, and in psychological discourse. Ultimately, prostitution infringes upon the most fundamental human right: the right to life and to live with dignity and purpose (Farley, 2003). The prostitute is a victim

of every bad thing man due to women: physical abuse, economic oppression and abandonment (LaSalle, 2012). Every woman in sex industry is virtually subjected to the torture, the rape, the murder, the beating, the despair, the hollowing out of the personality and the near extinguishment of hope (Margaret, 2022). Every inherent right of a human being is stripped away from women in prostitution. They are effectively enslaved, bought for their physical appearance, sexual organs, skin, and emotions, and exploited as commodities. The prostitution is practiced to institutionalize male domination (Dworkin, 1993). The practice of prostitution is a practice of objectification of women. Every act of sexual objectifying occurs on a continuum of dehumanization that promises sexual violence at its far end (Stoltenberg, 1993).

Women involved in prostitution endure significantly higher levels of violence compared to other groups of women. This is linked to societal constructs of masculinity, which are often centered on power and dominance. Male sexuality, shaped by these constructs, frequently manifests as an assertion of control over women. Such power dynamics are most easily imposed on women in prostitution, who are often marginalized due to poverty, social disadvantage, race, or a history of abuse. A woman paid for sex is looked down upon by society as the lowest of the low and is at the mercy of clients, police, lawmakers, and all kinds of moral guardians (Hofmann, Barbara & Arlie, 2004). Prostitution strips women of the inherent right to equality, compelling them to disconnect from their sense of identity and self-worth. Like slavery, prostitution is a lucrative form of oppression (Farley, 2006). Both slavery and prostitution are rife with every imaginable type of physical and sexual violence (Farley, 2006). Prostitution is one of the most graphic examples of men's domination over women. And thus, represents an institution that diverges from the feminist goal of equality for women (Zawisza, 2011).

3.1 Prostitution as Exploitation, not legitimate Labor

The practice of coercing individuals into prostitution is not a form of labor but a profound exploitation of human dignity. Prostitution undermines women's autonomy and integrity, encroaching their status and eroding their self-worth. It cannot be considered legitimate labor under any analytical framework; rather, it is a deeply entrenched system of exploitation. By commodifying sexuality, prostitution subjects women to stigmatization, stripping them of their individuality and creating conditions that dehumanize and marginalize them. This stigma extends to all women, perpetuating a narrative of inferiority within the broader human community. Prostitution inherently objectifies women, reducing them to instruments of sexual gratification. From the feminist conflict theory perspective, prostitution emerges not only as a consequence of women's economic marginalization but also as a product of a patriarchal societal framework. This framework perpetuates male dominance in heterosexual dynamics and continues to objectify women as mere instruments /sex objects of male pleasure (Barry, 1996). Recognizing prostitution as legitimate work is both inhumane and regressive, as it reinforces systemic inequalities and institutionalizes the sexual subjugation of women. Legalizing prostitution perpetuates the patriarchal and capitalist commodification of women's bodies, transforming them into mere saleable commodities and reducing sexuality to a mechanical stereotype. Violence,

inherent in prostitution, cannot and should not be framed as a form of wage labor. Prostitution should be recognized not as a form of work but as an expression of entrenched sexual exploitation that necessitates immediate abolition.

Prostitution has evolved into a significant industry within patriarchal capitalism, mirroring the structure of other capitalist enterprises. In this system, the profession is dominated and controlled by men. Unlike other occupations, the role of a female prostitute highlights the subordinate social and political position of women. Moreover, because people's bodies and sexual capacities are an integral part of their identity as men and women, the woman who works as a prostitute sells her womanhood and therefore herself (Pateman, 2007). Recognizing a woman's right to sell her own body does little to address the deeper issues of patriarchy and exploitation within the wage-labor system. Prostitution is nothing but a transaction in which one person (woman) must be defined as a social subordinate who caters to the desires of another (man). This is why a prostitute's work differs from that of other low-status workers in a sense that it is a form of labor that cannot be reciprocated (Christine Overall). Eventually, prostitution may corrupt non-market sexual relationships by promoting the valuation of women in terms of their market worth (Anderson & Radin, 2013). The 'Brothel Model' illustrates how women are subjected to sexual domination by men. Within this framework, women are portrayed as existing solely for sexual purposes, with their identities narrowly confined to their role in providing sexual services. This perspective entirely disregards their individuality, intrinsic personality, and human potential (Andrea Dworkin). Prostitution fundamentally represents exploitation and violence. The so-called sexual act performed by a man on the body of a woman in prostitution is an act of oppression, not mutual engagement; the notion of consent is merely a reflection of coercion, and the concept of labor in this context is an imposed subjugation rather than a genuine economic activity. Calls for legalization distort the profound suffering endured by those involved. From a Marxist feminist perspective, prostitution is viewed as a byproduct of capitalism. In this system, those at the lower rungs of the social hierarchy akin to the proletariat exchange their labor for survival, while the profits generated from their work benefit the ruling class. Similarly, in prostitution, the labor framed as sex work reduces the body to a commodity, and sex becomes a tradeable good, leading to further exploitation. This parallels wage labor, where essential human capacities are altered, resulting in dehumanization. Prostitutes, like wage laborers, find their value defined by market forces and are subjected to systemic exploitation by the dominant class.

Alienation, degradation, confinement, mistreatment, and disregard are inherent characteristics of prostitution, where women are effectively enslaved. The violation of liberty and freedom is a fundamental outcome, making prostitution an imposed status and a form of systemic exploitation. This practice undermines the essence of humanity, stripping individuals of their independent identity and reducing them to objects of commerce. The human rights violations experienced by women in prostitution and other forms of commercial sex are extensive, pervasive, and deeply troubling. Prostitution stands as one of the most egregious violations of women's human rights and cannot be legitimized as a form of labor. The harshest aspect of prostitution is the stigma it

perpetuates, which dehumanizes those involved and reinforces societal conditions that marginalize them. When these individual experiences are generalized, they lead to the broader devaluation of women, particularly those from marginalized groups like the Badi community, further undermining their dignity and autonomy.

3.2 Legalizing Prostitution?

The legal recognition of prostitution is a deeply contentious issue. The legal status of prostitution has been framed in various ways, including ‘abolition’, ‘decriminalization’, and ‘legalization’. The **legalization** or **decriminalization** of prostitution is an unethical, immoral, and unjust movement that goes against the rights of women. From a **human rights perspective**, the so-called sex trade is inherently structured around male dominance and control over sexuality. Prostitution operates as a marketplace where men are the sole buyers, and the exchange is exploitative resembling a predator-prey dynamic. As such, validating prostitution as a legitimate and acceptable profession is both cruel and inhumane. Prostitution exemplifies the sexual subjugation of women, and its legalization serves only to reinforce existing power structures, hindering progress towards equality and justice, while institutionalizing the sexual exploitation and oppression of women. Prostitution hinders the evolution of sexuality towards healthier, more life-affirming, and mutually respectful relationships between men and women. It undermines women’s autonomy and dignity. Within the sex trade, women are commodified and forced to sell sex according to the demands of clients and sex workers. In this transactional dynamic, the buyer’s preferences dominate, diminishing the rights and freedoms of the seller. The notion of “women’s body, women’s right” is often oversimplified, categorizing prostitution into voluntary and involuntary forms, without fully addressing the deeper exploitation inherent in the practice (Cecelia, Hofmann). When adult women choose to exchange sex for money, it is often seen as a personal decision within the context of a free and democratic society. However, the distinction between voluntary and involuntary prostitution reflects the exploitative, cannibalistic and predatory nature of a deeply unequal and stratified society.

The ‘distinction of voluntary and involuntary prostitution’ obscures the powerful structural socio-economic conditions like poverty, marginalization, lack of opportunity and prior sexual abuse that often drive women and children to engage in prostitution’ (Liberator, 2005). Women involved in prostitution often do so because they have no viable alternatives. Their options are largely shaped by the need to provide for themselves and their children. These decisions are better understood as survival strategies. Rather than willingly choosing prostitution, a woman in this situation is more likely to comply with the harsh constraints of her limited options. It is extremely wrong belief that legalization or decriminalization of the prostitution would dignify and professionalize women, in fact, this is a very great myth (Raymond, 2007). The legalization of prostitution serves to enrich pimps, traffickers, and the sex industry. By legalizing or decriminalizing prostitution, brothels, sex clubs, massage parlors, and other related establishments are transformed into legitimate businesses where commercial sexual activities are permitted to operate freely. This shift often leads to an increase in covert, underground, and street-based

prostitution. Moreover, the legalization of prostitution encourages sex trafficking and exacerbates sexual exploitation. Ultimately, the legalization or decriminalization of the sex industry benefits only the exploiters, further perpetuating the cycle of exploitation. Women in prostitution point out that legalization or decriminalization of the sex industry cannot erase stigma of prostitution, but, instead, makes women more vulnerable to abuse because they must register and lose anonymity (Daley, 2001). Similarly, Mary Sullivan and Sheila Jefferys have reported that the number of prostitutes without License has incredibly increased in Sydney after its legalization in 1995 (Sullivan & Jefferys, 2001). The legalization and decriminalization of the sex industry significantly and dangerously increases child prostitution. It has greatly facilitated the institutionalization and reinforcement of patriarchal stereotypes, leading to a heightened societal demand for prostitution. In each new generation, some women are conditioned to accept prostitution, often coming from backgrounds with limited opportunities for development and personal freedoms. Far from promoting women's health, the legalization of prostitution negatively impacts their physical well-being and psychological health. It does not foster women's ability to make independent decisions or enhance their capacity for rational choice. The legalization of prostitution does not promote women's ability to make rational decisions or exercise independent choice. Women in brothels generally do not support the legalization or decriminalization of prostitution.

Research conducted by Janice Raymond and colleagues for the US National Institute of Justice revealed that 67% of law enforcement officials and 72% of social service providers believed that women did not voluntarily enter prostitution. The lack of viable alternatives for many women involved in the sex industry challenges the notion that their participation is voluntary (Sullivan & Jefferys, 2001). The sex industry often leverages the distinction between forced and voluntary prostitution to create a semblance of legality and stability, which can be used to legitimize brothels, pimps, and prostitution itself. Marginalized women may struggle to prove coercion, further entrenching their victimization. An ILO report on the sex industry as a legitimate economic sector acknowledges that prostitution is one of the most alienated forms of labor, with many women expressing feelings of being forced into the work, experiencing guilt, and longing to depart from this. These realities underscore the grave violations of human rights faced by women in prostitution, and legalizing prostitution only exacerbates the violence, conflict, and exploitation inherent in the industry.

The 'Oppression model' asserts that legalizing prostitution would only solidify exploitation and abuse. Legalizing prostitution would significantly contribute to the institutionalization of patriarchal structures, reinforcing male dominance over women's sexuality in society. Involuntary prostitution is present whenever women or girls cannot alter their circumstances or escape, regardless of how they entered these situations, subjecting them to sexual violence and exploitation (Barry, 2015). Prostitution exacerbates violence and severe health issues for women. It is inherently cruel, exploitative, discriminatory, and inhumane, reducing women's bodies to commodities in the "flesh trade". Legalizing prostitution essentially enslaves women, turning them into targets for organized crime, leading to endless exploitation. Prostitution represents a violation of women's sexuality

and human integrity, and its legalization embodies the darker aspects of capitalist exploitation. The critical issue is not whether prostitution should be legalized, but rather how women involved in prostitution can assert their human rights and lead lives of dignity. Legalizing prostitution, in any form or approach, only accelerates sexual abuse and institutionalizes exploitation. Prostitution can in no way be legitimized or promoted as a means of advancing women's labor. Therefore, the urgent and essential action is to fully abolish prostitution and its associated practices.

4. THE GLOBAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The 1990s marked a rising acknowledgment of women's rights as fundamental human rights, forming an essential and inseparable component of universal human rights. Today, the United Nations remains crucial in safeguarding and advancing women's rights. The Charter of the United Nations represents a significant advancement so far as faith in and respect for human rights is concerned. The provisions concerning human rights run throughout the U.N. Charter "like a golden thread". Human rights would occupy a significant chapter in any story of the U.N. (Henkin, 1965). Members of the U.N. have committed themselves to promote respect for and observance of human rights and fundamental freedoms (Lauterpacht, 1950). The principle of gender equality has been universally acknowledged by the United Nations since the adoption of its Charter. Since then, the UN General Assembly has adopted numerous Resolutions, Declarations, and Conventions concerning the rights and status of women and the girl-child. The Commission on Human Rights established by the Economic and Social Council in 1946 was the "nearest approach to permanent machinery for the supervision of the problem of protection" of human rights (Brownlie, 1973). The Commission on the Status of women has done valuable work for promoting the rights of women in political, economic, civil, social and educational fields and in achieving the goal of women having rights equal to those of men (Brownlie, 1973). The Declaration has been celebrated as "a landmark event of immense importance and one of the most significant accomplishments of the United Nations". The core principles of the UDHR are: the Principle of Human Dignity, the Principle of Equality, and the Principle of Recognition as a person. The Universal Declaration provide that all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights (Article 2, UDHR). Although the UDHR is a declaration that does not require ratification and is regarded as soft international law, states remain bound by its provisions due to its customary law status and its recognition as Jus cogens norms.

The 1949 Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons and the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others stated in its preamble that prostitution, along with the associated evil of trafficking for prostitution, undermines the dignity and worth of the human person and poses a threat to the well-being of individuals, families, and communities. The Convention obliges its signatories to criminalize actions where an individual: (i) procures, entices, or coerces another person into prostitution, even with their consent; or (ii) profits from or exploits another person's involvement in prostitution, regardless of their consent. Each party to the Convention agrees to take all the necessary measures to repeal or abolish any existing law, regulation or administrative provision by

virtue of which persons who engage in or are suspected of engaging in prostitution are subject either to special registration or to the possession of a special document or to any exceptional requirements for supervision or notification (UN, 2000). All States Parties to the 1956 Supplementary Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, the Slave Trade, and Institutions and Practices Similar to Slavery are required to implement all feasible and essential legislative and other actions to achieve, as quickly as possible, the full eradication or discontinuation of such institutions and practices. This obligation applies regardless of whether these practices fall under the definition of slavery as outlined in Article 1 of the 1926 Slavery Convention. “Slave trade” means and includes all acts involved in the capture, acquisition or disposal of a person with intent to reduce him/her to slavery; all acts involved in the acquisition of a slave with a view to selling or exchanging the individual; all acts of disposal by sale or exchange of a person acquired with a view to being sold or exchanged; and, in general, every act of trade or transport in slaves by whatever means of conveyance (UN, 2000).

The cornerstone of the ICCPR (International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights), 1966, lies in the charter provisions addressing human rights and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948, widely regarded as the foundation from which all human rights instruments have been derived. The Article on covenant represent a total prohibition of slavery, slavery trade, servitude, forced or compulsory labour (Article 8, ICCPR); Right of all persons deprived of their liberty to be treated with humanity and with respect for the inherent dignity of the human person (Article 10, ICCPR); right to be recognized everywhere as a person before the law (Article 16, ICCPR); equality before law (Article 26, ICCPR). The States Parties to the ICESCR (International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights), 1966, commit to ensuring that the rights outlined in the Covenant are upheld without any form of discrimination based on race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinions, national or social origin, property, birth, or any other status. The Covenant recognizes the right to work freely chosen (Article 6, ICESCR); the work referred to in Article 6 must be decent work. This is effectively defined by the Covenant, which recognizes the right of everyone to the enjoyment of just and favorable conditions of work (Article 7, ICESCR); right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health (Article 12, ICESCR).

The inaugural global conference on human rights in 1968 resulted in the adoption of the Proclamation of Tehran and 26 resolutions. The Proclamation reaffirmed a commitment to uphold and implement the principles outlined in the United Nations Charter and other international human rights conventions. It also called upon all states to ensure the effective enforcement of these fundamental rights. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) of 1979 stands as the most extensive international treaty addressing women’s human rights. Often referred to as the Women’s Charter or an International Bill of Rights for Women, it focuses on gender equality and the status of women. CEDAW establishes codified legal standards specifically for women and integrates numerous principles related to women’s rights and equality. The Convention sets out a basic definition of discrimination against women as being any distinction made on the basis of sex which has the effect or purpose of impairing

the enjoyment by women of human rights and fundamental freedoms (Article 1, CEDAW), condemns the discrimination of women and enjoins the signatory countries to adopt legislative and administrative measures to eliminate and outlaw discrimination (Article 2, CEDAW). By ratifying the Convention, States pledge to implement a range of actions aimed at eliminating all forms of discrimination against women. These commitments include embedding the principle of gender equality within their legal frameworks, repealing discriminatory laws, and enacting suitable legislation to prohibit gender-based discrimination. Additionally, they agree to create tribunals and other public institutions to safeguard women from discrimination effectively and to take measures to eradicate discriminatory practices by individuals, organizations, or enterprises (UN, 2000). Hence, the Convention provides that States parties shall take all appropriate measures including legislation to suppress all forms of traffic in women and exploitation of prostitution of women. In a recent commentary on Article 6, the Centre for Human Rights of the United Nations affirms that states which tolerate the existence of exploitative prostitution, girl-child prostitution and pornography and other slave-like practices are in clear violations of their obligations under the Article (UN, 2000).

Similarly, the Convention requires States to address the problems of rural women; to improve the position of women in rural areas who are probably the most deprived, both economically and socially (Article 14, CEDAW). The General Recommendation No. 19 issued by the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW Committee) aptly recognizes sexual exploitation and trafficking as manifestations of violence against women and girls. It asserts that gender-based violence constitutes a form of discrimination, infringing upon women's fundamental human rights. The Recommendation further emphasizes that the scope of the Convention extends to both public and private acts, obligating governments to implement legal and other necessary measures to prevent such violence. Building upon these principles, General Recommendation No. 28 identifies the fundamental obligations of State Parties under Article 2 of the Convention, underscoring their duty to combat all forms of discrimination against women. Subsequently, General Recommendation No. 35 updates and expands upon the provisions of General Recommendation No. 19, reiterating the importance of promoting and safeguarding women's autonomy as an essential aspect of preventing gender-based violence and ensuring equality. The Optional Protocol to CEDAW, adopted in 1999, is an international treaty aimed at guaranteeing women the full and equal enjoyment of their human rights and fundamental freedoms. It also seeks to take effective measures to prevent any violations of these rights. Under the Optional Protocol, individuals or groups, subject to certain conditions, may file complaints with the CEDAW Committee regarding breaches of the treaty's provisions, provided all available domestic remedies have been exhausted.

The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) of 1989 obligates State Parties to uphold and protect the rights enshrined in the Convention for every child within their jurisdiction, without any form of discrimination. This commitment applies regardless of the child's or their parent's or legal guardian's race, color, gender, language, religion, political or other opinions, national, ethnic, or social origin, property, disability, birth, or any other status

(Article 2, CRC). States Parties shall take all appropriate legislative, administrative, social and educational measures to protect the child from all forms of physical or mental violence, injury or abuse, neglect or negligent treatment, maltreatment or exploitation, including sexual abuse, while in the care of parent(s), legal guardian(s) or any other person who has the care of the child (Article 19, CRC). States Parties undertake to protect the child from all forms of sexual exploitation and sexual abuse (Article 34, CRC). For these purposes, States Parties shall in particular take all appropriate national, bilateral and multilateral measures to prevent: the inducement or coercion of a child to engage in any unlawful sexual activity (Article 34(a), CRC); the exploitative use of children in prostitution or other unlawful sexual practices (Article 34(b), CRC); the exploitative use of children in pornographic performances and materials (Article 34(c), CRC).

States Parties shall take all appropriate national, bilateral and multilateral measures to prevent the abduction of, the sale of or traffic in children for any purpose or in any form (Article 35, CRC). States Parties shall protect the child against all other forms of exploitation prejudicial to any aspects of the child's welfare (Article 36, CRC). The Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution, and Child Pornography, 2000, requires State Parties to criminalize the sale of children, child prostitution, and child pornography as specified in the Protocol. In their reports, the Special Rapporteurs address the unique challenges faced by girl children regarding these issues.

The 'Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action' 1993, asserts that gender-based violence, along with all forms of sexual harassment and exploitation, including those stemming from cultural biases and international trafficking, are incompatible with human dignity and must be eradicated. The 'UN DEVAW, 1993' addresses the issue of violence against women, asserting that such violence violates women's fundamental rights and freedoms, undermining or negating their ability to fully enjoy those rights. It emphasizes the persistent failure to safeguard these rights in the context of violence against women and acknowledges that this violence reflects the historically unequal power dynamics between men and women.

These dynamics have led to male dominance, discrimination against women, and hindered women's advancement. The declaration also recognizes that violence against women is a key social mechanism that enforces their subordination to men (OHCHR, 2000). States should pursue by all appropriate means and without delay a policy of eliminating violence against women (OHCHR, 2014). The Beijing Platform for Action emphasizes the importance of addressing the root causes of trafficking and forced prostitution, urging States to take effective measures to tackle both internal and external factors that fuel the trafficking of women and girls for prostitution and other forms of commercialized sex. It affirms that women's human rights include the right to have control over their sexuality and to make decisions freely and responsibly, particularly concerning sexual and reproductive health, without facing coercion, discrimination, or violence. The platform also calls for gender equality in sexual and reproductive relations, where mutual respect, consent, shared responsibility for sexual behavior, and autonomy are upheld,

ensuring the integrity of the person is fully respected. The 'ILO Forced Labour Convention' 1930 (No. 29) defines "forced or compulsory labour" as any work or service demanded from an individual under the threat of penalty, where the individual has not voluntarily agreed to it. The Convention acknowledges the severe consequences of forced labour and calls for the total abolition of slavery. It covers both traditional forms of forced labour, such as remnants of slavery or slave-like practices, and more recent forms, including debt bondage and human trafficking, often referred to as 'modern slavery.' These practices violate human dignity, reflecting poor working and living conditions. The ILO's Core Principles include a non-discriminatory framework, an anti-exploitation stance, and a protective/corrective approach to combat forced labour (OHCHR, 2014).

The United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (2000) acknowledges that "trafficking in persons, especially women and children, for forced and exploitative labour, including sexual exploitation, stands as one of the most severe violations of human rights currently faced by the United Nations. This issue is pervasive and increasing. It stems from the social and economic circumstances in the victims' home countries, is perpetuated by discriminatory practices against women, and is fueled by a callous disregard for the suffering of those exploited for the services they are coerced into providing (UN, 2000). The fate of these most vulnerable people in the world is an affront to human dignity and a challenge to every State, every people and every community" (Annan, 2004).

The Protocol to Prevent, Suppress, and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children (2000), which supplements the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, defines exploitation to include at least the exploitation of others for prostitution or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or similar practices, servitude, or organ trafficking. States Parties are required to implement or enhance legislative and other measures, such as educational, social, or cultural initiatives, and to engage in bilateral and multilateral cooperation to reduce the demand that drives all forms of exploitation, particularly those affecting women and children, and leads to trafficking (UN, 2000).

The SAARC Convention on Preventing and Combating Trafficking in Women and Children for Prostitution (2002) underscores that the harmful practice of trafficking women and children for prostitution is a direct affront to human dignity and honor, constituting a violation of fundamental human rights. According to this Convention, 'Prostitution' is defined as the sexual exploitation or abuse of individuals for commercial gain. The Article 10 provides that the State Parties to the Convention shall adopt, in accordance with their respective Constitution, the legislative and other measures necessary to ensure the implementation of the Convention (SAARC Convention on preventing and combating Trafficking in women and children for prostitution). The SAARC Social Charter of 2004 asserts that gender discrimination contradicts human rights, undermines human dignity, and negatively impacts the well-being of both the family and society.

4.1 Legal Framework at the National Level and Institutional Measures

Area/ Legal References	Provisions/ Key Aspects
Constitutional Foundations and Basic Tenets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People’s sovereign right and right to autonomy. - Maintaining freedom, sovereignty, territorial integrity, national unity, independence and dignity of Nepal. - Eradication of all forms of discrimination and oppression resulted by the feudalistic, autocratic, centralized, unitary system of governance. - Dedicated to establishing an egalitarian society through democratic socialism, upholding civil liberties, human rights, rule of law, and promoting sustainable peace, good governance, and prosperity (Preamble, The Constitution of Nepal, 2072).
Equality, Liberties and Fundamental Freedoms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right to dignified living (Article 16). - Equality before the law (Article 18). - Right against untouchability and discrimination (Article 24). - Right against exploitation (Article 29). - Rights of women (Article 38) “ensures women’s equality in lineage rights, safe motherhood, reproductive health, and property rights. It guarantees equal participation in state bodies through proportional inclusion and access to special opportunities in education, health, employment, and social security based on positive discrimination. Furthermore, it protects women from all forms of violence or exploitation, guaranteeing legal punishment for offenders and compensation for victims”. - Rights of child (Article 39). - Rights of Dalit (Article 40). - Right to social justice (Article 42). - Right to social security (Article 43). - Right to constitutional remedies (Article 46). - Implementation of fundamental rights (Article 47).
National Civil Code, 2074(BS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Honor and recognition of Individuality/ Personality (Section 12, The Country Civil Code Act, 2074). - Prohibition of unlawful customary traditions (Section 15). - Equality before the law (Section 17). - Protection against discrimination (Section 18). - Provisions for special protections for marginalized groups, including women (Section 19).
National Penal Code, 2074(BS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Criminalizes acts of violence and discrimination, including rape, trafficking, prostitution, sexual abuses, slavery servitude, any inhuman treatment or customary malpractices (Sections 160, 162, 163, 166, 168, 119, 120, 213, Criminal and Penal Code Act, 2074).
Social Welfare Act, 2049(BS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government programs for the welfare of women, children, disabled, and backward communities. - Promotes gender justice and empowerment of women.
Human Trafficking and Transportation (Control) Act, 2064(BS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Criminalizes trafficking for prostitution and sexual exploitation, prohibits living off the earnings of prostitution (Section 2(e), Section 4(1) ,4(2), Section 15, Human Trafficking and Transportation Control Act, 2064).

Good Governance (Management and Operation) Act, 2064(BS)	- Provisions supporting positive discrimination include poverty reduction, social justice, women’s empowerment, gender equity, upliftment of marginalized communities, regional development, human rights protection, and inclusive participation in governance.
National women commission Act, 2063(BS)	- Safeguarding and advancing women’s rights and interests while integrating them into the development mainstream to ensure holistic progress and gender equity. - Monitors execution of laws related to women’s rights and supports legal assistance for victims.
Caste based Discrimination and Untouchability (Offence and Punishment) Act, 2011(AD)	- Criminalizes activities that discriminates people on the basis of caste or untouchability.
Labor Act, 2017 (AD)	- Ensures equal remuneration for work of equal value for men and women.
Legal Aid Act, 1995(AD)	- Provides free legal aid to indigent citizens, particularly women, in accessing justice.
Crime Victims Protection Act, 2018 (AD)	- Ensures justice for crime victims, particularly in cases of sexual violence.
Gender Equality Plans (Gender Equality and Social Inclusion Policy, 2009)	- Focus on mainstreaming gender in social and economic development. - Gender equality and women’s empowerment as a central aspect of national development
Sustainable Development Goal (2016-2030)	In 2015, Nepal aligned with United Nations member states by adopting the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), succeeding the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) as international development benchmarks. Nepal has made impressive progress in promoting gender equality and women’s empowerment (National Review of Sustainable Development Goals, 2015).
Supreme Court’s Contribution to Gender Justice (Case Laws)	The Supreme Court has provided significant contributions in the context of ‘gender justice.’ The Court has issued orders related to issues such as right to equality, principle of non-discrimination, right to privacy, right to profession, reproductive rights, right to identity, and women’s human rights. (Key Principles Affirmed by the Court)
Tek Tamrakar et al. vs. HMG, Secretariat of the Council of Ministers and Others (NKP 2005, Issue 6, Decision No. 7550).	Women of Badi origin, an ethnic minority in Nepal, often forced into prostitution, sought to rectify the common practice of denying citizenship and other rights to their children when the father cannot be identified. The Court ruled that denying citizenship was unconstitutional and amended a law that gave precedence to men in birth and death registrations. The Court ordered a study on the Badi community’s issues and required all recommendations to be implemented. - Harmony and tolerance cannot exist in a society with unequal and degrading treatment based on religion, caste, gender, class, or any other factor. A cohesive social system is indispensable for development. - No citizen should be deprived of the right to live a dignified life as enshrined in the Constitution, emphasizing public welfare, social justice, and individual human rights.

Rina Bajracharya et al. vs. HMG, Secretariat of the Council of Ministers and Others (NKP 2001, Issue 5, Decision No. 6898).	The Supreme Court held that human rights treaties ratified by Nepal have precedence over national laws as per the Treaty Act, 2047. The Court emphasized eliminating traditional discriminatory practices and distributing social justice from a gender perspective.
Lili Thapa vs. Prime Minister and Office of the Council of Ministers (NKP 2005, Issue 9, Decision No. 7588).	The Court affirmed that everyone's right to equality, freedom, and life is based on dignity and respect, and depriving women of these rights contradicts the principle of gender justice and universal norms of justice.
Gyanu Devi Rana vs. HMG (NKP 2075 BS, Decision No. 9943).	Trafficking in people and forcing them into prostitution undermines their human rights to live with dignity. The Court recognized trafficking as a heinous crime against humanity.
Advocate Sapana Pradhan vs. HMG (Writ No. 56, 2001, Decision Date: 2059/ 1/19 BS).	The Court ruled that punishment for rape cannot vary based on the character or occupation of the victim, specifically declaring the discriminatory provisions in the country code regarding sex workers' rape as invalid, asserting compliance with international human rights standards.
Advocate Narayan Jha vs. Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Kathmandu et al (NKP 2069, Issue 2, Decision no. 8765).	The Supreme Court held that the objective of the inclusive principle is to empower or provide reservation for those excluded from the state's mechanisms due to economic, social, educational, or cultural reasons. It further stressed that the state has an obligation to identify deprived groups.
Rajendra Dulal vs. Government of Nepal, Prime Minister and Council of Ministers (NKP 2072, Issue 1, Decision No. 9320).	The Court stated that it is the state's duty to make special provisions for positive discrimination, ensuring that unequal treatment is given to unequal groups to ensure real equality.
Advocate Amar Bahadur Shah vs. Government of Nepal, Prime Minister and Council of Ministers (NKP 2074, Issue 1, Decision No. 9574).	The Court provided a broader interpretation of positive discrimination, emphasizing social inclusion as essential for promoting the rule of law and democracy. It affirmed that the state's inclusive policy aims to integrate marginalized groups into government structures, promoting equitable behavior.
Advocate Mohan Shasankar vs. Nepal Vedha Vidhyashram Secondary School (Writ Petition Civil no. 824 of 1988, Writ Petition Criminal no. 745-54 of 1950; Case of Social Exclusion)	The Court ruled that any practice or effort that supports the continuation of traditional discriminatory practices benefiting a dominant social class is discriminatory and should not be accepted.

4.2 Insights and Key Discussions

The Badi system, a deeply entrenched social custom, continues to undermine human rights and perpetuate gender-based discrimination in Nepal. Despite constitutional mandate, legal provisions and policy efforts aimed at ensuring equality and empowerment, there is no specific legislation criminalizing Badi practice. The lack of effective legal frameworks and enforcement mechanisms has allowed the system to persist, subjecting women and children from the Badi community to systemic marginalization, including denial of citizenship, education, and access to government services. The Supreme Court of Nepal has played a proactive role in addressing these issues through landmark rulings, such as directing the government to facilitate citizenship in the mother's name and ensuring birth registration without paternal identity. However,

the implementation of these directives remains weak, leaving many Badi individuals in vulnerable conditions. Women and children continue to face discrimination, violence, and limited access to opportunities, perpetuating cycles of poverty and exclusion. Addressing this challenge requires a multi-faceted approach: enacting special legislation to criminalize the Badi system, ensuring effective enforcement of existing laws, and integrating a gender-sensitive perspective across legal and policy frameworks. Furthermore, adopting innovative judicial strategies, such as Epistolary Jurisdiction, could enhance access to justice for marginalized communities.

Nepal has been urged by international bodies, such as the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) and the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD), to fulfill its commitments to eradicate harmful practices, prevent exploitation, and promote the rights and dignity of all individuals, with particular emphasis on women from marginalized communities. Achieving gender justice and safeguarding human rights requires decisive action in these areas. However, Nepal falls short in complying with its obligations under the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), including General Recommendations 12 and 19 issued by the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women, as well as the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women. The Nepalese government has yet to establish comprehensive legal, political, administrative, and cultural frameworks to effectively combat violence against women. Urgent measures are needed to implement robust legislative, administrative, social, and educational initiatives aimed at protecting women and girl children from all forms of harm, including physical and psychological violence, neglect, abuse, exploitation, and mistreatment. This entails addressing critical issues such as sexual exploitation, sexual abuse, forced prostitution, the Badi system, harmful traditional practices, and criminalizing acts related to prostitution.

5. CONCLUSION

Men and women are not monolithic entities; they are shaped by diverse cultural, ethnic, and economic realities. Gender discrimination, a universal truth, perpetuates through power imbalances and patriarchal structures, posing threats to sexuality and autonomy. Violations of women's rights are often cloaked in the guise of tradition, religion, and cultural norms, justifying oppression under the banner of custom. In the Badi community, customary practices institutionalize prostitution, a form of sexual slavery that undermines human dignity. Prostitution, recognized as inherently exploitative, violates fundamental human rights, including the right to life, liberty, and bodily integrity. Legalizing prostitution perpetuates abuse, exacerbating human trafficking and gender-based violence. It reduces women to sexual objects, stripping them of autonomy and dignity. The 'Badi Pratha' normalizes such exploitation, equating to the legalization of prostitution under the pretense of cultural practice. This custom entrenches systemic violence, economic deprivation, and social marginalization, particularly against Badi women, who remain among the most disenfranchised groups in Nepal. Without targeted legal interventions, this structural exploitation will persist.

Prostitution is not merely an immoral act but a profound violation of women's human rights. Its eradication demands strict legal measures complemented by social reform and awareness. Laws alone cannot effect change; their effective implementation is crucial. The lack of specific legal frameworks addressing the plight of Badi women reflects systemic failures in Nepal's judicial and administrative systems. Badi women, like all women, are entitled to inherent dignity, equality, and autonomy. They are not commodities or vessels of exploitation but individuals with rights and identities. Prostitution and related customs violate these rights, perpetuating cycles of abuse, poverty, and discrimination. The state bears the responsibility to protect Badi women from structural exploitation. This includes enacting and enforcing laws that criminalize prostitution and eliminate harmful practices like Badi system. Legal reform must integrate social justice initiatives to address deep-seated inequities and promote gender equality. Human rights are indivisible; the denial of one right jeopardizes the integrity of others. Protecting women's rights, including those of Badi women, is not merely a legal obligation but a moral imperative. The eradication of prostitution and harmful customs requires a holistic approach that combines legal action with cultural, social, and economic transformation. It is only through such comprehensive measures that the Badi women, Badi community and society as a whole can attain true equity and justice. Nepal must now rise to address the rights and justice of Badi women and Badi community and take decisive action to eliminate prostitution as Badi pratha.

6. WAY FORWARD

To address entrenched cultural and societal practices like the exploitation of Badi women, a multifaceted and transformative approach is essential. Such practices persist due to the absence of logical scrutiny and historical context, perpetuating stereotypes and disregarding human rights, conscience, and egalitarian principles. The following measures are proposed to eradicate these injustices:

- **Scriptural Reevaluation:** Hindu scriptures must be reviewed to distinguish between constructive and harmful elements, retaining only those that align with equality and ethical practices.
- **Legal Interventions:** Customs and practices that promote exploitation, violence, or discrimination should be criminalized. The state must enact specific laws addressing the plight of Badi women, ensuring compliance with constitutional and international human rights standards.
- **State Responsibility:** Governments must prioritize protecting women and marginalized groups, reform discriminatory laws, and transform harmful socio-cultural norms. Effective mechanisms to monitor progress and ensure the enforcement of constitutional equality are critical.
- **Judicial Oversight:** The judiciary must actively safeguard the rights of exploited women, utilizing international human rights standards incorporated into national laws to combat exploitation.

- **Awareness and Education:** Comprehensive awareness campaigns and gender-sensitive curricula should address systemic biases, beginning at the grassroots level to foster social reform.
- **Socio-Economic Empowerment:** Skill development, vocational training, and income-generating programs should be implemented to empower disadvantaged communities economically and socially.
- **Inter-Agency Cooperation:** Collaboration between governmental and non-governmental organizations is vital to enhance law enforcement, capacity building, and resource allocation for addressing exploitation effectively.
- **Cultural and Structural Reform:** Gender mainstreaming, revisiting traditional norms, and promoting gender-neutral values are fundamental to achieving substantive equality and dismantling patriarchal systems.
- **Comprehensive Legal Reforms:** Mandatory gender audits of existing laws and policies should be conducted to identify and rectify discriminatory practices.
- **Community Engagement:** Human rights institutions should prioritize counseling, interaction, and advocacy to eliminate exploitative practices and ensure the dignity and reintegration of affected individuals.

A persistent and comprehensive approach encompassing legislative reforms, judicial activism, educational initiatives, and socio-economic empowerment is essential to eradicate structural inequalities, abolish the Badi system, and establish a truly egalitarian society. The Badi community must evolve into the community where prostitution and inhumane practices are entirely eliminated, enabling its members to live with full dignity and honor.

Footnote

- 1) From, "An unknown non-violent resistance of Badi People", 2007, <https://socialchange.org.np/an-unknownnonviolent-resistance-of-the-badi-people/>.

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